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Commissions and Relations: Re-Examining Reconciliation

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Abstract: The Report of the Royal Commission on Aboriginal People (1996) and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada (2015) are considered key documents in the context of Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples' relations in Canada. Poetic autoethnography is an innovative process that uses language and creative expression to research the experience of making sense of the tension. While I propose to neither definitively define nor offer solutions, the poem that emanates from the analysis represents a re-examination of reconciliation as it is broadly understood from the respective commissions, and how it is a specific lived experience in my research.

Keywords: Indigenous peoples in Canada; poetic autoethnography.

Introduction

The Report of the Royal Commission on Aboriginal People (RCAP, 1996) and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada (TRC, 2015) are considered key documents in the context of Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples' relations in Canada. Both reports chronicle the experiences and challenges of Indigenous peoples given the historical and more contemporary colonial project that has significant implications on their unique and diverse social, cultural, spiritual, and political identities. The Report of the Royal Commission on Aboriginal People (1996) and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada (2015) both include extensive recommendations to foster the reconciliation of Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples across all stakeholders of Canadian society. The 94 Calls for Action in the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada draw special attention

to addressing reconciliation on issues that have widespread significance, including education, language and culture, and health and justice, to list a few.

Yet, reconciliation remains a highly complex, difficult, and sensitive topic for Indigenous and non-Indigenous people alike. The Commissions have, however, forced a necessary revisitation to the personal, cultural, linguistic, institutional, and systemic tensions that are embedded in the inequities that challenge Indigenous peoples as they are described in both documents. It is timely, thus, to address these official Commissions using poetry as a unique expression of understanding to shed light upon the complexities inherent between Indigenous and settler-relations.

Research Context

I have read the respective reports carefully. In the process, I have paid attention to the four stages of Indigenous and non-Indigenous relations as the RCAP describes them, and how each underscores the marginalization of First Peoples in Canada (McGregor, 2011). I have noted, too, how the language of reconciliation (particularly as it is underscored in the Truth and Reconciliation Commission Report) is not necessarily always accompanied by focused action and commitment to change (Davis et al., 2017).

It is important, as well, to position myself in the research context. As a bi-epistemic researcher and settler-ally, I have had varied opportunities over the last fifteen years to collaborate with Indigenous colleagues, students, parents, and communities and learn first-hand about how reconciliation between Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples is necessary to move forward in a positive and sustaining manner. The words of the Elders that guided our work together were stark reminders of the nuanced understanding of Indigenous knowledge and how ways of knowing and being are central to Indigenous traditions and beliefs.

Moreover, I have come to appreciate the epistemic differences between knowledge and traditions. In the process, I have arrived at a better understanding of how education can be a most effective means to create the necessary conversations between the competing and complementary paradigms of non-Indigenous and Indigenous peoples (Cherubini, 2021; 2014). But I recognize, too, that this is not a simple task. I have been privy to the tense and difficult conversations in Indigenous communities that described how mainstream education policies and practices, as examples, have ignored Indigenous students' learning preferences and styles. The repercussions include feelings of marginalization for Indigenous students that quite simply do not see themselves represented in the social, epistemic, and cultural traditions of mainstream classrooms and schools. The inevitable tension that is an outcome of these marginalizing experiences have further adverse consequences that impede the same efforts to foster an authentic sense of reconciliation.

Poetic Autoethnography: Making Sense of the Tension

I have experienced research that exists in the complexities of these very tensions. I choose to share the experiences through poetry to convey to other researchers, scholars, and members of all communities the strong perceptions that emerge in creative expression. Autoethnographic poetry,

as a research method, is a product of self-reflection whereby even fundamental assumptions are questioned (Jones et al., 2013). Poetic autoethnography uses language and creative expression to research the experience of making sense of the tension (Leavy, 2020). My work using this research methodology has shed light upon thinking critically in a manner that represents a sustainable and promising explanation that might not always be as captively described in more empirical-based research methods. In some respects, an analysis of the two respective Commissions through the lens of poetic autoethnography represents a more particular experience with the content under investigation since it provides the researcher with the possibility to articulate their experience without the restrictions of conventional writing and methods.

While I propose to neither definitively define nor offer solutions, the poem does in fact represent a re-examination of reconciliation as it is broadly understood from the respective Commissions, and how it is a specific lived experience in my research.

How do we measure influence?

Is it described?

Is it prescribed?

How do we interpret control?

Is it measured?

Is it imposed?

From what constructs are our actions carved?

Do we serve speculation?

Or is compliance served to us?

Do we internalize constraint?

Or are limited to expression.

Perhaps to understanding?

Truth.

Ours?

And theirs?

Do we invite provocative unease?

...

It may just be simpler to live by the prevailing norms,

and benefit from advantage.

From opportunities to secure emotional

intellectual

physical

spiritual

safety.

To react with reverence to realities that shape the future.

Our future.

Their future too?

Is it even well-understood?

Or fully told?

For whom?

To whom?

To (un)intentionally ignore the unspeakable mysteries of the margins,

and recoil from experiences of discomfort

that trouble the notions of acceptance.

Of status quo.

To borrow from ways already justified.

Indifference to those silenced as a consequence of our Knowing.

Knowing better.

To signal our attention to social justice,

when such measures are self-socially justified.

Ours is an interesting identity, you know?

A collective of faces.

A myriad of voices.

Ambitious initiatives to fulfill the obligation of progress.

Not necessarily driven by a search for alternatives.

Alternative Wisdom.

Alternative Relations.

Alternative Being.

Are these even possibilities?

The opportunity to build meaning from inexperience.

To encounter the reality of questions.

And the prudence to transfer what is intuitive.
To deal exclusively with enabling awareness.
To deliberate the widening of narrow ways.
To develop a mindful insistence on obscurity.
The interpretation of fluency ...
Of expectations ...
Of possibilities.
To exist together.
Different, but the same.
The relative complexity of unexamined thought
And of humbly getting along in the world.

Conclusions

Autoethnographic poetry presents researchers with possibilities to share understandings and critical reflections in a manner that is not inhibited by more formal research conventions. The topic of reconciliation, for both settlers and Indigenous peoples alike, remains as timely as it is sensitive. Reconciliation deserves our focused attention. The First Peoples of this land are deserving of the attention not only across national platforms, but local and individual ones as well.

Poetic autoethnography may in fact be a most viable approach for future research, since it welcomes individuals to intimately experience the topic and then advance their understanding and reflections with others and open the door to further inquiries and possibilities. Future research may invite settlers and Indigenous communities to adopt autoethnographic poetry in order to consider holistically and fully the range of emotions, perceptions, and experiences that are outcomes of the implications of official policies and commissions that will, in turn, lend themselves to better understand what it means to reconcile differences and “humbly get along in the world.”

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